

replications. Soil was clay loam, with low available N, medium available P and K, and pH 7.5.

Basal CCU (1%) and NCU (5%)

yields were not significantly different from that with PU in splits.

Yields with SCU broadcast and USG deep point placed 2 d after transplanting

were not significantly different from that with split applications of PU.

Split-applied urea was the least expensive practice. □

Applying nitrogen with sesbania

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Yields with and without sesbania green manure and three levels of N as urea in different splits were studied in a field experiment laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications during 1986 kharif. Soil was a sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.2, EC 0.15 dS/m, organic C 0.34%, total N 0.06% Olsen's P 10 kg/ha, and a percolation rate of 5 mm/h.

Sesbania grown in situ for 7 wk was incorporated 1 d before transplanting. Sesbania dry matter was 24 t/ha, with

Sesbania plus N effects on yield. Ludhiana, India, 1986 kharif.

Treatment	N application (kg/ha) at indicated time			Grain yield (t/ha)
	0 DT	21 DT	42 DT	
No sesbania + no N	—	—	—	4.8
No sesbania + 120 kg N/ha	40	40	40	7.4
No sesbania + 180 kg N/ha	60	60	60	8.2
Sesbania + no N	—	—	—	7.0
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	60	—	—	8.1
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	—	60	—	7.8
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	30	—	30	8.1
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	30	30	—	7.7
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	—	30	30	8.4
Sesbania + 120 kg N/ha	—	60	60	8.4
Sesbania + 120 kg N/ha	40	40	40	9.0
LSD (P = 0.05)				0.4

106 kg N/ha. All plots received 26 kg P and 23 kg K/ha at the final puddling.

Sesbania green manure plus 60 kg N/ha yielded more than sesbania with 120 kg N/ha (see table). Applying 60 kg N/ha

in 2 equal splits at 21 d and 42 d after transplanting (DT) was most efficient.

If 120 kg N/ha is applied with green manure, 3 equal splits at 0, 21, and 42 DT gave the highest yield. □

Responses of rice to N, P, and Zn in semireclaimed alkali soil

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P deficiency has been a major cause of low yields in semireclaimed alkali soils. We studied the effect of P fertilization with N and Zn in a semireclaimed alkali

Effect of P application with N and Zn on yield in a semireclaimed alkali soil. Karnal, India.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Zero	17.5 kg P	Mean
N 120 Z 0	4.9	5.2	5.0
N 160 Z 0	5.2	5.3	5.2
N 80 Z 20	4.5	5.0	4.8
N 120 Z 20	5.4	6.6	6.0
N 160 Z 20	5.8	7.5	6.6
N 200 Z 20	5.7	7.1	6.4
Mean	5.2	6.1	
LSD (0.05)			
N		0.72	
P		0.36	
N × P		ns	

soil. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications.

Half the N and all the P and Zn were applied at transplanting as urea, single superphosphate, and zinc sulfate. The remaining N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. Recommended agronomic practices were followed.

Originally the soil had been highly sodic (pH 10.45), but gypsum application and 4 yr cropping had reduced pH to 8.8, EC to 0.42 dS/m,

and exchangeable sodium percentage to 19 in 0-15 cm surface soil. The soil had loamy texture, 0.28% organic C, 2.73% CaCO₃, 0.5 mg DTPA-Zn/kg, 76 mg available N, 3.96 mg available P, and 140 mg available K/kg.

Applying N and Zn without P had no effect on yield. Applying N, P, and Zn together significantly increased yield (see table). A balanced application of 160 kg N, 17.5 kg P, and 4.5 kg Zn/ha gave the maximum yield. □

Effects of several urea-based N sources

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We compared 6 urea sources — prilled urea (PU), urea supergranule (USG), large granule urea (LGU), neem cake-coated urea (NCU), rock phosphate-

coated urea (RPU), and sulfur-coated urea (SCU) — at 37.5, 112.5, and 150 kg N/ha in a 1986 dry season field experiment. Soil was a fine loamy hyperthermic Typic Haplaquept with pH 5.3, organic C 0.46%, CEC 4.3 meq/100 g, 215 kg available N/ha (alk. permanganate method), 6.5 kg available P/ha (NaHCO₃ extract), and 37 kg available K/ha (ammonium acetate extract). The experiment was in a split-